

THE LABYRINTH OF IRONY IN BASHKIM SHEHU'S NOVEL THE CIRCLE

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Abstract

This paper examines the role of irony in Rrethi (*The Circle*) by Bashkim Shehu, one of the most prominent contemporary Albanian writers. Through intertextual references, most notably to Goethe's *Faust* and a labyrinthine narrative structure, Shehu employs irony as a key literary device to critique totalitarianism and its lingering psychological effects. The analysis highlights the interplay of dramatic and situational irony, revealing how characters' perceptions of freedom, salvation, or control clash with the grim realities of dictatorship and moral enslavement. In particular, the protagonist's belief in liberation through collaboration with the Secret Service exposes the paradox of self-imposed captivity. Situational irony also emerges in the destruction of communist police files, which, rather than offering closure, deepens collective anxiety. By intertwining symbolism, intertextuality, and irony, Shehu exposes the contradictions of memory, guilt, and survival in post-communist Albania, situating *The Circle* as both a postmodern and politically engaged work.

Keywords: irony, labyrinth, faust, dictatorship, postmodernism.

Bashkim Shehu's fiction

Bashkim Shehu was born on June 22, 1955, in Tirana. Currently residing in Barcelona, Spain, he is one of the most prolific writers of contemporary Albanian literature. Besides being a writer, Shehu is also recognized as a significant translator. His literary journey began in his youth, but his most notable creative output and success came after the 1990s. He has authored numerous stories, novellas, and novels, enriching Albanian literature in various ways. Shehu's works primarily focus on the communist period in Albania, exploring the individual's experience under the totalitarian regime and the system's effects in different forms. He has written and published systematically since the fall of communism in Albania.

Irony

Irony is one of the most significant rhetorical and literary devices, accompanying humanity since antiquity. At its core, irony serves as a tool to create tension between what is said and what is implied, engaging the reader or listener in the process of deconstructing or uncovering hidden meanings beyond the literal. Irony has always been present in various stages of human history because it has served as an essential means of communication. "Irony seeks to dictate something concealed: it shuts the door but leaves a key hanging on the side, visibly displayed on its lock, inviting those who pursue it and guiding them on how to act in order to encounter it" (Schoentjes 128).

Irony as a Critique of Totalitarianism in Rrethi (*The Circle*)

The novel *Rrethi* (*The Circle*) is a typical postmodern and essentially ironic novel. It consists of seven parts that are interconnected through symbolism. The author has also referred to it as a labyrinth novel with seven entrances. This novel has a close intertextual relationship with Goethe's *Faust*. This is clearly seen from the very beginning of the novel through the chapter titles, which resemble those of *Faust*, as well as through the ideological framework and even the names of the characters. Through symbolism and metaphors, the author, using subtext and intertextual references to various literary texts, explores dictatorship, the

individual, various events of the time, and the consequences of the system. The parts of the novel are not connected in terms of plot, but rather through the overarching symbolism that extends throughout the subtext of the work. The novel naturally contains different types of irony, including dramatic irony and situational irony.

"In truth, I am already dead. No cure be it through radiation or medication and no prayer or talisman can bring me relief from this illness that has overtaken me and is consuming me day by day. I can feel, even as if I can see with my own eyes, the extensions of that black fungus that has sprouted inside me, somewhere between the pit of my chest and my abdomen." (Shehu 4)

In this fragment, the narrator who believes he is already "dead", reveals his fatalistic worldview: The narrator's belief that he is metaphorically dead foreshadows his eventual physical and spiritual demise. The reader understands that his "death" is both literal (the disease) and symbolic (his moral decay under communism), but he remains trapped in his delusion of control. The self-aware narration reflects postmodern irony, where the act of storytelling becomes a futile attempt to impose meaning on a meaningless existence.

"It wasn't something that enslaved me—on the contrary, it was precisely this that made me feel free, as it offered me an invisible support, like the wings of fate, and thus limitless, almost divine possibilities to fulfill all my desires. That's what I believed back then, and I wasn't mistaken." (*The Circle*, 32)

The character believes that his writing is a symbolic salvation, a way to give even more meaning to his life. However, the reader grasps the deeper subtext, understanding the underlying source of the idea behind this writing. The character in the novel does not manage to escape from his guilt or his Faustian fate, as he is already spiritually dead.

"What I am writing now, or rather, what I have already finished writing, encompasses everything that has been, is, and remains meaningful." (*The Circle* 110-111)

Situational Irony

Situational irony occurs when there is a stark contrast between expectations and reality. "Talking about Situational Irony means talking about the kinds of situations we see as ironic and also, therefore, about the observer's sense of irony, his attitudes, and responses. As I have said, one way of being ironical is to invent and present ironic situations, but an ironist who presents ironic situations will have much the same sense of irony, attitudes, and responses as the ironic observer" (Muecke 43). According to Katharina Barbe, "Situational irony pitches situations against each other. Nevertheless, the differentiation between verbal and situational irony is not discrete. Verbal irony does not appear in a vacuum, only in a situation. Thus, even though instances of irony can be inherently more language-related, verbal irony cannot and should not be discussed devoid of its situation" (Barbe 77).

"And so, bit by bit, as the sign of my fate becomes visible - that meaningful and all-encompassing sign which is this dream where I conquered instead of being conquered by a woman, this dream of dreams that replaces all women at once, this hydra that replaces all hydras with its heads gnawing at me as they twist inside me - this sign of fate that unfolds in this narrative, in this precise tracing of the monster writhing within me, or this sign of the labyrinth where you turn and return always to the same place, because every place replaces all places, and which is the Evil with a capital E within me from which I could never separate myself." (The Circle, 110)

In this passage from the novel *The Circle*, the "Walpurgis Night Dream" can be interpreted as a symbol of salvation, but in reality represents a curse. Faust views the dream as a redemptive artistic vision, when in truth it serves as a metaphor for his corruption - the "hydra" devouring him from within represents the indelible guilt for his betrayal of Margarita and of himself.

In the novel *Rrethi (The Circle)*, the author presents profound situational irony that reveals the psychological terror and moral contradictions of a difficult period in Albanian society, particularly during and after the dictatorship era. The narrative focuses on people's rumors about the destruction of secret police files. The central situational irony lies in how the supposed "cleansing" of these archives actually perpetuates the regime's psychological control, as the disappearance of documents doesn't liberate citizens but rather traps them in perpetual suspicion.

"For the first time, I felt truly terrified during the wave of changes, when word spread about an attempt by the Ministry of Internal Affairs, still in communist hands to destroy files. There were claims that the files were being burned right in the ministry courtyard, where, as rumored, flames had been seen leaping up the walls and reaching toward the sky during one night." (The Circle, 45).

Shehu constructs another layer of situational irony through the protagonist's conflicted position. As a former informant, he simultaneously hopes for the files' destruction and fears it. The passage about the archives reveals the ultimate situational paradox: the narrator, who once believed his collaboration would leave no trace, now confronts the permanence of his signed confession, making him vulnerable in the new era he had hoped would bring freedom.

References

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